

Annual report CAA Netherlands-Flanders chapter (CAA-NLFL) 2017

Board:

Chair: Ronald Visser

Secretary: Jitte Waagen

Treasurer: Devi Taelmans

During the annual CAA meeting in Atlanta several people from the CAA-NLFL chapter were present and contributed with various papers.

This year we did not manage to hold our annual meeting due to a lack of organizational capacity. This also means that we didn't have an official general meeting. To compensate for the lack of a formal public event and meeting our members, we will organize a day of workshops in cooperation with the Digital Archaeology Group from Leiden University in April 2018.

Due to the lack of a meeting in 2017, there are no financial reports to present.

We have been in close contact with CAA-Germany in relation to the upcoming joint meeting in Bochum in 2018, which appears to be going well.